

Providing Uroandrogical Care to Children in the Republic of Uzbekistan

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 05 July 2022	Currently, there is a high incidence of children and adolescents in the Republic of Uzbekistan, including in the uroandrogical field with high risks of male infertility (up to 35%). The factor of male infertility takes the leading positions and is a source of childlessness in 40% of cases. These statistics inexorably indicate that this is the essence of links in one chain, namely, the absence of a specific organization of specialized medical care in the field of reproductive health of boys and adolescents. For the new Uzbekistan, solving the issues of prevention of male reproductive diseases in childhood is vital.
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INTRODUCTION

According to the world literature over the past few years, the frequency of infertility has approached 22%, reaching a critical level, and 40-60% of patients with disorders of the reproductive system are men [1, 2]. Currently, important attention is paid to the preservation of the reproductive health of children and adolescents.

It is important to point out the fact that if the pediatric gynecological service is currently developed at all stages of medical care, then the situation regarding uroandrogical care for children requires more careful study and attention.

It is also necessary to pay attention to the key role of a general practitioner and a pediatrician in the early diagnosis and detection of reproductive health disorders in children, since they are the first to examine a child after his birth and are able to send a child to a pediatric uroandrogologist in a timely manner. At this stage, the level of awareness of primary care specialists in the reproductive health of children is important [3, 4].

At the moment, there is regulatory control in institutions of pediatric uroandrogical care, which reflects the sequence of medical care in this area, and also clearly describes the necessary standards in the work of a pediatric uroandrogologist [5]. However, there is still a need to analyze

the processes that prevent the reduction of the incidence of reproductive function in children at the regional level.

THE PURPOSE OF THE RESEARCH

Study of aspects of the organization of uroandrogical service in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Providing uroandrogical care to children at a new level includes a number of related and complementary elements:

- close cooperation of polyclinic doctors, pediatric somatic, nephrological, urological and surgical hospitals;
- introduction of endoscopic diagnostic methods of research and surgical treatment of children with malformations of the genitourinary system;
- optimization of the main methods of research and treatment as they become available with their introduction into clinical practice.

A service for providing uroandrogical care to children has been established and is functioning in our country, starting with outpatient polyclinic, inpatient inter-district and regional organizations and ending with the republican specialized scientific and practical medical center of urology in Tashkent.

The pediatric uroandrogology service of the Republic of Uzbekistan is represented by the following stages [6, 7]:

– The first stage of providing pediatric uroandrological care consists of district pediatricians and pediatric surgeons of the polyclinic. The main purpose of this stage is to identify children with uroandrological pathology and treatment of uncomplicated infections of the genitourinary tract;

– The second stage includes pediatric urologists of city polyclinics, whose tasks include the provision of specialized consultative and diagnostic medical care. In some regions, as part of the interdistrict children's urological or surgical departments, separate beds have been allocated for children with uroandrological diseases, where simple surgical interventions are carried out;

– The third stage includes regional hospitals, where advisory points have been created and beds for children with uroandrological diseases have been deployed as part of children's urological and surgical departments. In each area there is a main freelance specialist in pediatric urology. At this stage, all the necessary clinical and laboratory, functional and radiological research methods are carried out, surgical interventions are carried out for congenital anomalies of the development of the genitourinary system in children;

– The fourth stage is the republican center of Pediatric urology. In this center, patients are referred who need complex diagnostic methods and treatments that cannot be carried out at previous stages.

After analyzing the results of treatment, emergency medical care is provided mainly at the regional level to patients with acute uroandrological pathology and surgical aid for diseases of the scrotum, cryptorchidism, varicocele and other anomalies of the external genitalia. The range of surgical interventions has expanded in all regions of the republic, plastic surgery is more often used in children with pathology of the upper urinary tract. Modern methods of surgical interventions such as laparoscopic and endoscopic technologies have been introduced.

This center is equipped with endoscopic and urodynamic equipment. There are diagnostic departments equipped with modern technologies for ultrasound, X-ray, laboratory and radionuclide diagnostics. Endocrinological, nephrological and resuscitation departments are involved in the diagnostic and therapeutic process. Some patients with uroandrological profile are transferred after surgery to the above-mentioned departments to continue conservative and physiotherapy treatment.

The tasks facing pediatric urologists of our republic in the coming years:

- optimization and implementation of minimally invasive methods such as laparoscopy and endoscopy for congenital pathologies of the genitourinary system in children in all regional hospitals;
- improvement of staffing and training of outpatient and inpatient centers of pediatric urology;
- modernization of the material and technical base at the level of regional and republican centers of

pediatric urology.

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, the solution of the presented tasks and the innovative organization of medical care will create conditions for high-quality and affordable medical care in the direction of pediatric uroandrology, which in general is already manifested at the level of reproductive health of men in the region.

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